

Simulation of Continuous Arc with Semi-implicit Scheme and Mesh Adaptation

Gabriel Barreau¹, François Pechereau², Benjamin Khier¹, Julien Vanharen⁴, Philippe Lalande¹

Fabien Tholin¹, Guillaume Puigt³, Frédéric Alauzet⁴

¹Université Paris-Saclay, ONERA DPHY, F-91123 Palaiseau

²GammaO, Equipe Inria-ONERA, DPHY, ONERA, Université Paris-Saclay F-91120 Palaiseau France

³GammaO, Equipe Inria-ONERA, DMPE, ONERA, Université de Toulouse F-31055 Toulouse France

⁴GammaO, Equipe Inria-ONERA, Centre INRIA Saclay, Université Paris-Saclay F-91120 Palaiseau France
gabriel.barreau@onera.fr

Abstract— In this work, modeling a continuous arc powered by a pointed cathode and a flat anode was carried out. For this simulation, a new semi-implicit scheme was implemented in the MHD code Taranis developed at ONERA. This semi-implicit method is derived from an existing method dedicated to perfect gases. In this work, it was extended to real gases. To significantly reduce the computational costs represented by 3D meshes, the Taranis code is coupled with feflo.a, an anisotropic mesh adaptation framework developed at INRIA. After the presentation of this new workflow, it is validated with the 3D simulation of a free-burning arc in argon.

Keywords— Continuous arc, semi-implicit scheme, MHD, mesh adaptation

I. INTRODUCTION

During a lightning strike to an aircraft, the lightning current is composed of intense pulse currents of hundred thousand amperes and few hundred microseconds of duration, superimposed on the continuous current which lasts several hundred milliseconds [1]. During the continuous current, the lightning arc generates a low Mach number flow in the airflow. Conversely, the pulse currents produce shockwaves characterized by high Mach numbers flows. The numerical study of these two phenomena is generally conducted using separate solvers: incompressible solvers for the continuous current and compressible solvers for the pulse currents. This makes it difficult to model the phenomenon in a single simulation.

This work presents a numerical method capable of solving low and high Mach numbers flows in lightning arcs, enabling the simulation of all lightning current waveforms. In the literature, semi-implicit compressible methods are a promising candidate. They include an implicit pressure calculation, effectively removing the acoustic component from the time step constraint. This significantly increases the allowable time step value, leading to simulation times for the continuous phase of a lightning strike comparable to those obtained with incompressible solvers [2].

A semi-implicit method of this type has been implemented in the 2D/3D MHD code TARANIS. This implementation was

used to simulate a well-documented reference case of a 3D free-burning continuous arc in Argon [3] which can serve to validate our development. To minimize the computational cost of 3D simulations, the TARANIS code is coupled with feflo.a, an anisotropic mesh adaptation code developed by INRIA [4]. This mesh adaptation approach strategically refines the mesh only in regions where it is necessary. The effectiveness of this method has already been well-established in purely aeronautical applications and simulations of high current pulsed arcs on composite materials [5]. We aim to demonstrate its applicability in simulating continuous lightning arcs.

In the first part, the MHD code Taranis will be presented, along with the equations that will be solved. Next, the method for handling real gases will be explained, followed by the semi-implicit scheme to solve the fluid equations. The principle of anisotropic mesh adaptation methods will be presented. Finally, modeling of a free-burning arc configuration in Argon will be shown to validate the Taranis code's ability to model continuous arcs.

II. TARANIS CODE

Taranis is a finite-volume compressible resistive MHD code that can compute in the fluid domain the complex motion of a compressible and conductive fluid such as air plasmas under the influence of electromagnetic fields and radiative fluxes assuming a local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE) of the plasma. Under these assumptions and inside the fluid domain, this physical process is described by the coupled system of equations (1-6).

Conservation equation:

$$\partial_t \rho + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Momentum conservation equation:

$$\partial_t (\rho \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_v + \mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B} \quad (2)$$

Energy conservation equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t(\rho E_t) + \nabla \cdot ((\rho E_t + p)\mathbf{v}) \\ = \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_v \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot (\kappa \nabla T) + \mathbf{j} \cdot \mathbf{E} + S_{rad} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Electromagnetic equations :

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{j} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \mathbf{E} = -\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \nabla \varphi = 0 \quad (4) \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{A} = \mu_0 \mathbf{j} \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

Radiative transfert equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (\kappa_v^{-1} \nabla G_v) = 3\kappa_v (G_v - 4\pi L_v^0(T)) \quad (6)$$

Where $\rho(kg \cdot m^{-3})$ is the gas density, $\mathbf{v}(m \cdot s^{-1})$ the velocity vector of the gas, $p(Pa)$, the pressure, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_v(Pa)$ the viscous stress tensor, $\mathbf{j}(A \cdot m^{-2})$ the current density, $\mathbf{B}(T)$ the magnetic field, $E_t(J \cdot kg^{-1})$ the total energy per unit mass, $\kappa(m^2 \cdot s^{-1})$ the thermic diffusion coefficient, $\mathbf{E}(V \cdot m^{-1})$ the electric field, $S_{rad}(W \cdot m^{-3})$ a radiative source term, $\varphi(V)$ the electric potential, $\mathbf{A}(T \cdot m^{-1})$ the magnetic vector potential, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ the electrical conductivity (S/m), $\kappa_v(Hz)$ the absorption coefficient at frequency ν , $G_v(W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot Hz^{-1})$ the spectral incident flux at the frequency ν , and $L_v^0(W \cdot m^{-2})$ the black body spectral emittance at frequency ν and temperature T .

Note that inside solids such as electrodes, the heat transfer, and electromagnetic equations can be solved with specific balance equations at the interface between solid, liquid, and gas domains.

In the first step, Taranis solves inside the fluid domain the compressible Euler or Navier-Stokes equations (1-3) to compute the fluid dynamics, pressure, and temperature fields. Two electromagnetic source terms are accounted for: the Laplace forces $\mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B}(N \cdot m^{-3})$ in the momentum conservation equation (2), and the Joule effect $\mathbf{j} \cdot \mathbf{E}(W \cdot m^{-3})$ in the energy conservation equation (3). Taranis computes the transport, thermodynamic, and radiative coefficient properties in a second step with the updated temperature and pressure fields from a tabulated table. The inferred electrical conductivity σ is used in the current conservation equation (4). Then this elliptic equation is solved in solid, liquid, and gas domains with a linear solver to determine in a first step the electrical potential φ from which the current density \mathbf{j} and the electric field \mathbf{E} are derived. The magnetic field \mathbf{B} is computed by solving the Maxwell-Ampere equation (5) reformulated in magnetic vector potentials, resulting in three linear systems to solve. Finally, the new electromagnetic source terms are updated for the next iteration.

Due to the extreme temperatures ($T > 35000K$) and pressures ($P > 100bar$) occurring in the early stages of a pulsed arc phase, the Radiative Transfert Equation (RTE) is solved in Taranis to consider the fastest redistribution of the energy due to the emission and absorption of radiations in the plasma. A P1 approximation is used to solve the radiative

transfer equation (6) for each spectral band. For any couple (P, T), the radiative band is split in a given number equivalent spectral band (depending on the plasma gas investigated), in which a Rosseland mean of the absorption coefficient κ_v is done. The Rosseland mean is considered because air plasmas in the lightning arc are optically thick.

III. REAL GAS PROCESSING

Real gas processing is being considered by using tabulated thermodynamic data. These tables are generated using an ONERA code called Sethi [5]. Thermodynamical quantities of arbitrary mixtures are evaluated from partition functions assuming local thermodynamic equilibrium and perfect gas law. Energy levels for neutral and ionized atoms are taken from the NIST database [5]. Particle interactions are introduced in the model as partition functions and are truncated using the minimum value between the Fermi and Griem cutoff.[6]. Plasma composition at a given pressure and temperature is obtained by minimization of the mixture Gibbs free energy. Transport coefficients are computed according to the Chapman-Enskog theory [7] with quantities depending on the binary collision integrals and corresponding interaction potentials. Analytical expressions for collision integrals with Debye-screened coulomb potential are used for charged-charged interactions [8]. Neutral-neutral and neutral-charged collision integrals are evaluated using tabulated fits from [9].

IV. SEMI-IMPLICIT SCHEME

The numerical scheme is a spatial and temporal first-order finite-volume compressible method. The starting point for this method is described in published work by Boscheri et al [11], [12] and Allegrini [13]. The method possesses asymptotic preserving (AP) properties, allowing it to remain stable and accurate even when the flow becomes low-Mach. In summary, the scheme's construction is done by applying a flux separation operator in the energy equation [14], allowing the appearance of convective terms and acoustic terms. The convective terms will be solved explicitly, while the acoustic terms will be solved implicitly using an IMEX method [15] at the first order of accuracy:

$$\rho^{n+1} = \rho^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\rho u)^n \quad (7)$$

$$(\rho u)^{n+1} = (\rho u)^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\rho u^2)^n - \Delta t \nabla p^{n+1} \quad (8)$$

$$(\rho E_t)^{n+1} = (\rho E_t)^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho u^3 \right)^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\rho u h)^{n+1} \quad (9)$$

The scheme is carried out in 3 steps:

- Resolution of explicit convective flux, where the convection is evaluated with Rusanov-type approximate Riemann solver:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho^{n+1,exp} &= \rho^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\rho u)^n \\ (\rho u)^{n+1,exp} &= (\rho u)^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\rho u^2)^n \\ (\rho E_t)^{n+1,exp} &= (\rho E_t)^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho u^3 \right)^n \end{aligned}$$

- By inserting the momentum equation (8) into the energy equation (9), we obtain an implicit equation for pressure:

$$\begin{aligned} (\rho e_t)^{n+1} - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (h^{n+1,exp} \nabla p^{n+1}) \\ = (\rho E_t)^{n+1,exp} - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\rho u h)^{n+1,exp} \\ - \frac{1}{2} (\rho u^2)^{n+1,exp} \end{aligned}$$

With e_t the internal energy.

- Correcting the momentum and energy equation with the new pressure:

$$\begin{aligned} (\rho u)^{n+1} &= (\rho u)^{n+1,exp} - \Delta t \nabla p^{n+1} \\ (\rho E_t)^{n+1} &= (\rho E_t)^{n+1,exp} - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\rho u h)^{n+1} \end{aligned}$$

In this way, the calculation of the time step used in explicit compressible schemes:

$$\Delta t_c = CFL \frac{\Delta x}{\max(|v| + c)} \quad (10)$$

Becomes :

$$\Delta t_u = CFL \frac{\Delta x}{\max(|v|)} \quad (11)$$

With c the sound speed in the domain.

To illustrate the capabilities of the semi-implicit scheme in compressible flow configurations, we model the configuration of a Sod shock tube [16]. In this setup, at initialization, a membrane separates two different states on the left and right within a domain of size $x \in [0,1]$:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho = 1, u = 0, p = 1 \quad \text{if } x < 0.5 \\ \rho = 0.125, u = 0, p = 0.1. \quad \text{if } x \geq 0.5 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1 compares the density profiles for the first-order explicit compressible HLL, second-order HLL, and first-order semi-implicit model. A fourth solid line represents the reference solution. The simulations were conducted on a mesh consisting of 200 points, and $CFL = 0.5$. The time step used with the semi-implicit scheme is $\Delta t_u = 2.7e^{-3}s$, whereas in the case of the HLL model the time step $\Delta t_c = 1.14e^{-3}s$. We can observe that the semi-implicit method (blue dash) has similar results to those obtained with the HLL method of the first order (red points), which is consistent with the fact that the SI method is also of the first order. Therefore, the SI method has the characteristics of a classical compressible explicit method of first order for compressible flows.

Figure 1: Density profile calculated using a first-order HLL scheme (red points), a second-order HLL scheme (green dash and points), and the present semi-implicit scheme (blue dash). The calculations are performed on a mesh of $N=200$ points, and the final time is set at $t_f = 0.2s$.

The previous section showed that the first-order semi-implicit scheme provides results similar to those of the first-order explicit compressible method for compressible flows. The purpose of this section is to study the behavior of the scheme in the case of a weakly compressible flow (low Mach number flows).

In the case of a DC-powered electric arc, the fluid dynamics of the arc can be modeled by a column of hot fluid advected in space. To illustrate the advantages of the semi-implicit method compared to explicit models, we simulate the configuration of a hot column initialized with a Gaussian temperature profile with a maximum of 8000K in the middle of the domain. The domain is initialized with a constant pressure of 1 bar and a velocity $u \ll c$, $u = 10m/s$. A first modeling is done on a grid of 1000 points ($\Delta x = 1e^{-3}m$) with the semi-implicit method of first order, which will be compared with the results of an HLL method of second order. The real gas model is used where the gas considered is Argon.

Figure 2 shows the temperature curves for the semi-implicit and second-order explicit methods. Although the SI method is only first-order, its results are much less diffused than the explicit second-order method. To illustrate this phenomenon, this configuration is also simulated using the semi-implicit model with a time step value equal to that used by the HLL scheme Δt_c (equation 10). The time step used by the SI scheme (blue dash) is $\Delta t_u = 3e^{-5}s$, whereas the time step of the explicit scheme (red dash and dots) and semi-implicit (green dots) is $\Delta t_c = 2e^{-7}s$. This means that to reach the final time, the simulation with the explicit method and SI method with the explicit time step Δt_c will be at least 100 times slower than the simulation with the SI scheme Δt_u . As can be seen from Figure 2, the curve associated with the SI scheme using an explicit time step Δt_c (equation 10) has diffused more than the one using a semi-implicit time step Δt_u (equation 11). However, the first-order SI scheme using the same time step as the

second-order HLL scheme is still much less diffusive than the second-order HLL scheme.

Finally, we study the mesh convergence of this flow for both the SI method and the second-order explicit method. To facilitate this study, all diffusive effects of viscosity and thermal effects are not considered, which implies that the only remaining diffusion is the one originating from the numerical scheme. In this way, convergence will be achieved when the peak temperature value is the same as at initialization.

In Figure 3, the temperature profiles calculated by the SI method for different meshes are plotted, and it is observed that the SI scheme reaches convergence with a mesh of 20,000 points. In contrast, Figure 4 shows the temperature profiles calculated by the explicit method. The convergence is much harder to achieve since it is still not reached even with 50,000 points. This result demonstrates once again the advantages of the SI method, as it allows for the use of much larger time steps while achieving mesh convergence with coarser meshes.

Figure 2: Temperature of a hot column of 8000K advected at the speed $u=10\text{m/s}$ at $P=1$ bar with a mesh of $N = 1000$ cells. Viscous and thermal diffusion are not considered. The black solid line is the temperature at the initialization of the calculation. Explicit time step Δt_c (equation 10) was used for the HLL second-order scheme (red dash and dots) and SI scheme (green dots), whereas a semi-implicit time step Δt_u (equation 11) was used for the SI scheme (blue dash).

Figure 3: Study of the mesh convergence of a column at 8000K advected at a speed of 10m/s in 1 bar modelled with the SI model. The blue dash represents results at 1000 cells, the red dots results at 10000 cells, the green dash-dot results at 20000 cells and pink dash-dot-dot results at 30000 cells.

Figure 4: Study of the mesh convergence of a column at 8000K advected at a speed of 10m/s in 1 bar modelled with the HLL second-order model. The blue dots represents the results at 10000 cells, the red dash-dot-dot the results at 20000 cells, the orange solid line results at 30000 cells and green dash the results at 50000 cells.

V. ANISOTROPIC MESH ADAPTATION

Recent progress has matured anisotropic tetrahedra mesh adaptation to provide automatic control of estimated errors, which have been verified by code-to-code comparison. Alauzet documented the dramatic progress made during the last decade for anisotropic solution-adaptive methods to resolve simulations with shocks and boundary layers [4]. The adaptive computations use Hessian-based interpolation error estimates based on fully unstructured tetrahedral meshes. This method yields an anisotropic prescription of optimal meshes that are independent of geometric complexity. The mesh adaptation is based on the metric concept and the continuous mesh theory.

The details of this framework are given in [17] and [18]. Here, the main strategy is just recalled to tackle time-accurate mesh adaptation for unsteady simulations. An innovative mesh adaptation strategy for time-dependent problems based on a fixed-point algorithm was proposed in [19]. The main goals are to control of spatial and temporal interpolation errors during the whole simulation and reduces the number of mesh adaptations because error introduced by the transfers of solutions mainly drives accuracy. This strategy starts with the observation that direct extension of steady adaptation algorithms to unsteady problems is not appropriate: specific algorithms must be developed that truly consider the transient nature of the solution. It relies on the assumption that the temporal error is always controlled by the spatial one, which is indeed the case when solving, with an explicit time-integration, a linear advection problem under a CFL condition [20]. The fixed-point time-accurate anisotropic mesh adaptation algorithm relies on:

1. a global fixed-point mesh adaptation algorithm to converge the mesh adaptation non-linear problem,
2. the extension of the multi-scale error estimate [17] to unsteady problems by proposing a L^p space-time error analysis,
3. a conservative solution transfer operator to considerably diminish the error introduced by this stage of the algorithm,
4. a high-quality anisotropic local remeshing controlling the heights of the elements to guarantee optimal solver time steps and to ensure maximal robustness in the meshing process. This issue has been handled with care in [21].

The proposed approach overcomes all the problems relative to mesh adaptation for time-dependent simulations such as the mesh latency for the solution, the time-accurate error estimate, and the error reduction due to solution transfer from one mesh to another. In the present paper, the interpolation error is controlled by a scalar variable, namely ρE in the L^2 norm. In the course of the adaptation process, sequences of meshes that minimize the interpolation error in space and time are generated. This mesh adaptation framework is composed of a flow solver, here the MHD code Taranis, a metric-based error estimate, and a mesh adaptation code called feflo.a. The code feflo.a is still developed in Alauzet's team Gamma at INRIA France, and it summarizes efforts for more than ten years. A comprehensive description of the algorithm developed and used in feflo.a can be found in [22,23,24].

VI. FREE BURNING ARC WITH MESH ADAPTATION

In [25] a 3D modeling of a pulsed arc striking a composite panel was carried out using a compressible explicit method with mesh adaptation while comparing the obtained results with experimental data [26]. The results, showing a successful comparison with experiments, demonstrated the capacity of the Taranis code to model pulsed arcs in 3D with anisotropic mesh adaptation.

Unfortunately, the explicit compressible scheme used is not suitable for flows associated with continuous arcs due to very

small time steps and excessive numerical diffusion in low Mach flows. This is why this semi-implicit compressible scheme has been investigated to simulate both the continuous and pulsed current.

This section aims to demonstrate a first step in the validation of Taranis MHD code to simulate 3D arc in complex geometry by using the new semi-implicit scheme coupled with mesh adaptation. The validation case selected is a steady free-burning arc in Argon between a pointed tungsten cathode and a plate-shaped copper anode. This case is associated with a very low Mach number flow where compressible explicit solvers are not well adapted. This well-known configuration has been mainly investigated with Argon gas, for which numerous experimental [3] and numerical results [27], [28] [31] are available. These references will be used for comparisons and validations of our model.

Several assumptions will be considered:

- The plasma is considered to be in LTE (Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium).
- The electrodes will be cooled 1000K to prevent vaporization effects.
- Sheath effects are not currently considered at the electrode interfaces.

Figure 5 shows the 3D geometry of the configuration and the numbers identifying the boundary conditions. The nature of the boundary conditions is detailed in Table 1

Figure 5: Geometry and boundary conditions numbers for the free-burning arc configuration

Variable	BC 1	BC 2	BC 3	BC 4	BC 5	BC 14	BC 13
φ	0	N	N	N	N	X	X
A_x	0	N	N	0	0	X	X
A_y	0	0	0	N	N	X	X
A_z	N	0	0	0	0	X	X
G_v	0	0	0	0	0	X	X
<i>fluid</i>	X	X	X	X	X	N.S.W	N.S.W

Variable	BC 7	BC 8	BC 9	BC 10	BC 11	BC 12
φ	N	N	N	N	N	1
A_x	N	N	0	0	0	0
A_y	0	0	N	N	0	0
A_z	0	0	0	0	N	N
G_v	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>fluid</i>	Sb.O	Sb.O	Sb.O	Sb.O	Sb.O	X

Table 1: Boundary conditions of free burning arc. “N” refers to the Neumann boundary condition, “0” and “1” are Dirichlet boundary conditions, “Sb.O” refers to a subsonic outlet, and “N.S.W” refers to a no-slip wall with the temperature imposed at 1000K.

At initialization, the entire domain is at 1000K. The initialization of the arc is done by making a time-limited ($t=20\mu s$) conductive channel between the electrodes with a maximum value of electrical conductivity of $\sigma = 700 \text{ S.m}$. The current amplitude is set at 200A at the beginning of the modelization. The distance between the tip of the cathode and the anode is 1cm.

Bands	Frequency [$\times 10^{14} \text{ Hz}$]	Wave length [μm]
1	0.666 – 2.5	4.5 – 1.2
2	2.5 – 19.2	1.2 – 0.16
3	19.2 – 38.2	0.16 – 0.08
4	38.2 – 66.9	0.08 – 0.04
5	66.9 – 99.9	0.04 – 0.03

Table 2: Spectral band of Argon used in the radiative transfer model for $T \in [500, 35000] \text{ K}$ and P at 1bar and 2bar.

For the present work, numerical results for real gases in the following sections have been obtained for an argon gas composed of Ar, Ar⁺, Ar²⁺, Ar³⁺, and electrons. Both thermodynamical and transport quantities have been compared to available data from [29] and show good agreement over temperatures ranging from 300 K to 30000 K and pressures from 1 bar to 100 bar.

For Argon 5 spectral bands are used resulting in 5 elliptic equations in the form of equations (6) to solve. The 5 spectral bands are detailed in Table 2, ranging from mid-infrared to extreme ultraviolet.

The Navier-Stokes equations are solved in this flow, the viscosity terms are solved explicitly while the terms corresponding to thermal effects are solved implicitly. The radiative effects are solved with a P1 method. The resolution of radiative effects with a P1 method rather than with a net

emission coefficient method, which is conventionally used in this configuration [27] [28][31], arises from the desire to model a complete lightning strike. Since the resolution of radiative effects in the case of a pulsed arc cannot be done with a net emission coefficient method, a P1 method must also be used for the continuous part. The adaptation criteria used to adapt the mesh is the energy ρE_t . The results obtained will be compared with those of [31].

In Figure 6, the temperature isocontours are plotted in a cross-section along the X-axis. These isocontours have values between 11000K and 21000K, which corresponds to the temperature ranges calculated by [31]. It is observed that the well-known characteristic bell shape has been reproduced. The bell shape of the flow can also be seen in Figure 8, where the temperature iso values for 11,000, 13,000, and 20,000K are plotted. These 3D iso values allow us to illustrate the cylindrically symmetrical nature of this flow. Thus, it can be concluded that despite the entirely different schemes, i.e. compressible and unsteady in these works and incompressible at steady state in [27][31], the macroscopic properties of the flow (isocontour shape and maximum temperature range) have been well reproduced.

Figure 7 shows the appearance of the adapted mesh and shows the benefits of anisotropic mesh adaptation. Following the flow dynamics, the adaptation process only meshes where necessary which greatly reduces the number of points in the domain and significantly reduces the simulation time compared to a simulation on a fixed mesh. To illustrate the contribution of mesh adaptation in this configuration of 350,000 cells where the minimum cell size is set to $50\mu m$, using a fixed mesh made up of tetrahedral would have required around fifty million cells to achieve the same accuracy.

Figure 6: Isocontours with temperatures between 11000 and 21000K of a free-burning arc in Argon. The current amplitude is set at 200 A and the distance between the tip of the cathode and the anode plate is 1 cm.

Future work will include modeling a pulsed arc using the new semi-implicit scheme, and arcs in an air plasma to get closer to the objective of modelling a complete lightning strike.

Figure 7: Adapted mesh containing 350000 points with an adaptation criterion based on ρE . The meshes are refined near large gradients in the flow (close to the electrodes) and that they are coarser far from the flow.

Figure 8: 3D temperature iso values at 11000 (blue), 13000 (green), and 20000K (grey).

VII. CONCLUSION

To conclude, in this work, modeling of a continuous arc was carried out. To carry out this study, several key developments needed were made. First, a semi-implicit scheme was adapted to handle real gases, allowing the modeling of low Mach flows with a compressible method without being constrained by excessively small-time step values. Additionally, it was shown that these methods, in the case of low Mach flows, are much less diffusive than a second-order explicit method, even though the semi-implicit method is only first-order. A 3D configuration modeling of a continuous arc contained between a pointed cathode and a flat anode was simulated. To reduce computational costs, anisotropic mesh adaptation was used. This process allows meshing according to the flow dynamics, significantly reducing the number of cells in the domain. In the future, pulsed arc modeling with the new scheme is planned, and lightning modeling in the air will be studied.

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